

1 Title:
2 Timing of subsurface heat magnitude for the growth of El Niño events
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25 Geophysical Research Letters
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30 The subsurface heat buildup in the western tropical Pacific and the recharge phase in equatorial heat
31 content are intrinsic elements of El Niño-Southern Oscillation, leading to changes in zonal wind stress, sea
32 surface temperature and thermocline tilt that characterize the growing and mature phases of El Niño (EN)
33 events. Here we use numerical simulations to study the impact on subsequent EN episodes of a sudden
34 increase or decrease in ocean heat content during the recharge phase, and compare results with previous
35 studies in which this perturbation is prescribed earlier during the tilting mode. We found that, while not
36 substantially affected by the phase at which a sudden rise in heat content is prescribed, the timing and
37 magnitude of the events are very sensitive to the phase at which a major decrease is imposed. The different
38 response to the phase of increases and decreases substantiates the importance of non-linear subsurface ocean
39 dynamics to the onset and growth of EN episodes, and provides insight into the irreversibility of the events at
40 different stages of the oscillation.

43 Introduction

45 El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO) is the dominant variability mode at interannual timescales
46 (Wang and Picaut 2004), a primary source of seasonal-to-interannual climate predictability (Chen et al. 2004,
47 Izumo et al. 2010, Barnston et al. 2012, Petrova et al. 2016) and a key factor explaining large-scale
48 teleconnections (Ballester et al. 2011) with global impacts (Ballester et al. 2013, 2016a). The dynamics of ENSO
49 arise from a complex interaction between the atmosphere and the ocean in the tropical Pacific (Bjerknes et al.
50 1969, McPhaden et al. 2006), involving upper and lower level atmospheric winds, ocean waves traveling along
51 the equatorial thermocline, zonal redistribution of surface and subsurface ocean temperatures, and meridional
52 recharge or discharge of the tropical ocean heat content (Suarez and Schopf 1988, Jin 1997, Picaut et al. 1997,
53 Weisberg and Wang 1997, Fedorov et al. 2015).

54 ENSO is typically characterized by its two main opposite phases, El Niño (EN) and La Niña (LN),
55 which define an anomalous warming or cooling of Sea Surface Temperatures (SST) in the central and eastern
56 tropical Pacific, respectively. EN (LN) is always preceded by a meridional recharge (discharge) of basin-wide
57 tropical ocean heat content about 2 to 3 seasons in advance, which deepens (shoals) the whole equatorial
58 thermocline and warms (cools) the ocean subsurface at about 100 to 150 meter depth (Meinen and McPhaden
59 2000, Ramesh and Murtugudde 2013). This phase is in turn typically led by the tilting mode, a maximum
60 (minimum) in the slope of the equatorial thermocline explained by the strengthening (weakening) of the
61 equatorial trade winds and the subsequent anomalous downwelling (upwelling) of surface warm (subsurface
62 cold) waters in the western Pacific warm pool (Wyrčki et al. 1985, Ballester et al. 2015).

63 The leading paradigm explaining the oscillatory nature of ENSO, the recharge oscillator, emphasizes
64 the delayed effect of the enhancement (weakening) of the equatorial trade winds that precedes the recharge
65 (discharge) phase. Thus, the off-equatorial wind stress curl controls the change rate in equatorward subsurface
66 convergence (divergence) of water masses in the central Pacific, and therefore the tendency towards the
67 deepening (shoaling) of the thermocline (Jin 1997). Once the equatorial trade winds return to their
68 climatological values, westerly (easterly) wind bursts can occur and trigger eastward-traveling downwelling
69 (upwelling) Kelvin waves that deepen (shoal) the thermocline in the eastern Pacific, suppress (enhance) the
70 coastal upwelling there and activate the growth of an EN (LN) event (Ballester et al. 2016b). This succession of
71 phases is however subject to sources of irregularity, so that it is nowadays widely accepted that ENSO is a
72 slightly damped periodic oscillation modulated by stochastic noise (Kessler 2002).

73 Ballester et al. (2016c) recently studied the sensitivity of EN to a rise or fall in ocean heat content 21
74 months earlier by means of an ensemble of numerical simulations. These experiments showed that basin-wide
75 uniform warm equatorial SSTs follow a major increase in heat content, which favor the occurrence of a very
76 strong EN event one year later. The simulations also showed that the heat content of the system is naturally
77 restored after an initial major decrease, the resulting EN event is however delayed by up to one year. In the
78 present study, we extend this analysis with a new set of numerical experiments, in which we use exactly the
79 same methodology, but initial conditions are modified at a later stage of the onset of EN. More specifically,

80 we compare these two families of simulations with the aim of identifying the dynamical mechanisms that
81 explain how differences in the lead time of a sudden rise or fall in heat content affect subsequent EN events.

84 Methods

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86 The model used here is the Community Earth System Model (CESM) v1.2 (Hurrell et al. 2013). The
87 atmospheric component has a resolution of 2.5° in longitude and 1.875° in latitude, with 30 vertical levels. The
88 ocean model uses a displaced pole grid with approximately 1° resolution in longitude and 0.5° in latitude,
89 which is refined within the tropical band up to 0.25° at the equator. There are 60 vertical levels, with vertical
90 resolution decreasing from 10 m in the upper 150 m to 250 m in the deep ocean.

91 An EN episode with the same magnitude as the recent 2015/16 event (i.e. Niño3.4 Index = $+2.8^\circ\text{C}$) was
92 chosen from a reference (REF) 100 year spin-up simulation, which is validated against the composite of the
93 1972/73 ($+2.5^\circ\text{C}$), 1982/83 ($+2.6^\circ\text{C}$) and 1997/98 ($+2.7^\circ\text{C}$) EN events in the ORAS4 (Balmaseda et al. 2013) and
94 NCEP/NCAR (Kalnay et al. 1996) reanalyses (here referred to as observational composite, and labeled as OBS).

95 We describe a new family of ensemble experiments with initial conditions corresponding to a lead
96 time of 11 months before the December peak of this event (i.e. January 1st of year 0), and compare the results
97 with a family initialized 10 months earlier (i.e. March 1st of year -1, simulations reported in Ballester et al.
98 2016c). We note that these stages of the episode correspond to an early phase of the basin-wide deepening of
99 the thermocline (referred here to as RP, standing for Recharge Phase) and the maximum in the slope of the
100 equatorial thermocline (TM for Tilting Mode), respectively.

101 In each of these families, the intensity of the initial subsurface warm anomaly was decreased (negative
102 sign) or increased (positive sign). The warm temperature anomalies were fully modified only in the inner
103 three-dimensional box $[120\text{E}-80\text{W}] \times [10\text{S}-10\text{N}] \times [50-200\text{m}]$, and this modification was linearly decreased to
104 zero from the border of this inner box to the frontier of the outer box $[100\text{E}-60\text{W}] \times [15\text{S}-15\text{N}] \times [20-300\text{m}]$. Each
105 set of experiments in turn consists of 10 simulations with slightly perturbed initial conditions.

108 Results

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110 The comparison with the observation composites (Figures 1a, 2a, 3a) shows that the REF simulation
111 correctly reproduces the main dynamical processes preceding the peak of the observed major EN events and
112 the subsequent transition towards LN, including the main subsurface ocean features and the coupling between
113 the ocean surface and the atmosphere (Figures 1b, 2b, 3b). The model, for example, simulates the slow but
114 steady pile up of subsurface warm waters in the western Pacific near and above the thermocline, due to
115 stronger-than-normal easterly trade winds in the central Pacific during year -1, and the associated downward
116 heat advection in the warm pool (Figures 1c, 2c, 3c). Some differences are however found, e.g. the westerly
117 wind anomalies are stronger in the model than in the observation composites during the growing and
118 decaying phases of EN, which in turn explains the warm SST bias in the central Pacific (Figure 2c). The
119 differences between the observational composites and the REF simulation are however relatively small for the
120 type of dynamical processes and empirical relationships that are the focus of the present work, which are to a
121 large extent associated with the onset of the EN episodes in the ocean subsurface several months before their
122 mature phase.

123 The transition from the initial tilting mode to the recharge phase (i.e. the two stages that are here
124 compared) is seen to be associated with anomalies in the wind stress curl, which, according to the recharge
125 theory, generates equatorward subsurface convergence of water masses in the central Pacific, and therefore
126 the tendency towards the overall deepening of the thermocline (Jin 1997). Figure 4 shows that the
127 interhemispheric difference (northern minus southern hemisphere) of the tropical wind stress curl is negative
128 throughout year -1 in the whole basin, as well as in the central and eastern Pacific during the stages of largest
129 warming rate in year 0. Ballester et al. (2016b) showed that a fraction of this subsurface warming is additionally
130 explained by zonal and vertical advection of heat along the subsurface currents near the tilted thermocline.
131 We note that positive anomalies in interhemispheric wind stress curl difference also coincide with the

132 eastward-propagating subsurface cooling tendency and the associated transition towards LN conditions in
133 year +1 (McGregor et al. 2012).

134 In agreement with the observational composites, the initial conditions in the RP experiments were
135 prescribed at the beginning of the last month in which the ocean surface and the atmosphere are in a neutral
136 phase in the REF simulation (e.g. last month with slightly negative values of the Niño3.4 Index; Figure S1b).
137 Just a few months later, in early spring of year 0, the first strong westerly wind anomalies develop in the warm
138 pool (dashed green line in Figure 2b): as a result, the downwelling Kelvin waves start to cross the basin (Figure
139 3b) and the accumulated subsurface heat reaches the eastern Pacific (Figure 1b). The timely prescription of
140 subsurface heat content anomalies in the RP experiment just before the activation of the Bjerknes feedback is
141 therefore designed to provide some insight into the irreversibility of the EN event at this advanced stage of
142 the oscillation.

143 A sudden reduction of 80% in the heat content stored in the ocean subsurface during the recharge
144 phase (i.e. experiment RP-80%) does not significantly modify the dynamical mechanisms that precede the peak
145 of the episode in the REF simulation (Figures 1d, 2d, 3d, S1). As a result, the timing of the subsequent EN event
146 remains essentially unaffected, and the anomaly of the Niño3.4 Index reaches +1.15 °C, which represents a
147 nearly proportional relative decrease of about 60%. The maximum in westerly wind and SST anomalies is
148 however found to occur earlier, in August of year 0, so that the heat content in the basin is completely
149 discharged by the end of the year and the Niño3.4 Index returns to values close to 0 in March of year +1. The
150 fast and early termination of the event generates very weak cold subsurface temperature anomalies and no
151 reinforcement of the trade winds in the warm pool, which explains the lack of a LN event by the end of year
152 +1.

153 The dynamics of ENSO in the RP-80% experiment are completely different from those resulting from
154 the ensemble of simulations in which the same fraction of the heat content is removed during the tilting mode
155 10 months earlier (i.e. TM-80%). Ballester et al. (2016c) showed that in these runs a weak LN event develops at
156 the end of year -1, which re-activates the generation of the subsurface heat buildup in the western Pacific and
157 leads to a strong EN episode that peaks in December of year +1 (Niño3.4 Index = +2 °C). Differences between
158 both cases therefore highlight the importance of the timing of the prescribed decrease in heat content (Figures
159 1e, 2e, 3e). When this reduction occurs during the tilting mode, the system is forced to take a step back and
160 restore the heat content; if the decrease occurs just before the maximum of the recharge phase, the system is at
161 a point of no return in which the remaining heat is immediately released to the eastern Pacific, leading to a
162 weak EN event. Differences in the timing of the initial reduction in heat content and the eventual occurrence
163 of a restoring process have a substantial effect on the magnitude of the subsequent EN event, with the event
164 occurring with one year of delay in TM-80% and being almost twice as large than the one in RP-80%.

165 The response of the coupled ocean-atmosphere system to a sudden amplification of 80% in the heat
166 content during the recharge phase (i.e. experiment RP+80%) is immediate, with the excess heat being released
167 as eastward-traveling downwelling Kelvin waves and leading to an event of very strong magnitude at the end
168 of the year (Niño3.4 Index = +4 °C; Figures 1f, 2f, 3f, S1). A similar immediate release of the excess heat was
169 described in Ballester et al. (2016c) for the TM+80% experiment 10 months earlier, but in that case, the surface
170 warming at the end of year -1 was found to be uniformly distributed along the equatorial Pacific. Under these
171 conditions, the Bjerknes feedback cannot be activated, and therefore the initial warming only represents a
172 transition step towards a very strong EN episode of similar magnitude one year later. For this reason, even if
173 there are important differences in the involved dynamical mechanisms, anomalies in atmospheric winds, heat
174 content and surface and subsurface temperatures and currents are relatively similar between the two
175 experiments (Figures 1g, 2g, 3g).

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178 Discussion and summary

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180 Previous studies have argued that there exists a boreal winter barrier in equatorial Pacific upper ocean
181 heat content predictability due to a seasonal minimum in overall variability (Balmaseda et al. 1995, McPhaden
182 2003), in addition to the well-known boreal spring barrier in atmosphere and surface ocean ENSO
183 predictability. As a result of this boreal winter barrier, equatorial Pacific upper ocean heat content anomalies
184 in boreal autumn and early winter (i.e. September to January) do not necessarily persist until the following

185 winter season, while anomalies that exist in late boreal winter and spring (i.e. February to May) tend to persist
186 for the next 2 to 3 seasons (McPhaden 2003). Because of this, equatorial heat content anomalies in boreal
187 autumn and early winter are not necessarily associated with ENSO events the following year. We have here
188 chosen January of year 0 as a particularly relevant time of the year to prescribe a sudden change in heat content,
189 in order to test the inertia of the oscillation to perturbations in the evolution of subsurface temperatures. On
190 the one hand, it follows the boreal winter barrier in equatorial Pacific upper ocean heat content predictability,
191 whose role can be evaluated through the analysis of the differences between the TM and RP experiments. On
192 the other hand, it precedes the boreal spring barrier in atmosphere and surface ocean ENSO predictability,
193 and therefore it provides information about the irreversibility of the coupled ocean-atmosphere system.

194 A sudden increase or decrease in heat content can indeed occur at any time of the year, regardless of
195 the phase of the ENSO oscillation. For example, Hu and Fedorov (2016) showed that a fast increase in heat
196 content followed the January-to-March 2014 westerly wind bursts in the western Pacific, and a major decrease
197 occurred immediately after the unusually strong basin-wide easterly wind burst in June 2014. These changes
198 were relatively fast given that wind bursts generated Kelvin and Rossby waves that modified the depth of the
199 thermocline as they were traveling along the zonal axis. This type of increase (decrease) in heat content is
200 different from the meridional recharge (discharge) occurring during the mature phase of LN (EN). According
201 to the recharge theory (Jin 1997), the off-equatorial wind stress curl determines the tendency towards
202 equatorward mass convergence (poleward mass divergence), and therefore the recharge (discharge) in
203 tropical heat content through the meridional displacement of water masses. In this case, however, given that
204 only the tendency is determined by winds, this process is relatively slower.

205 The present work highlights the asymmetry between the impact of a sudden increase or decrease in
206 ocean heat content on subsequent EN events. We find that the timing and magnitude of the episodes are not
207 substantially affected by the phase at which a sudden rise is prescribed:

- 208 - TM+80%: peak in year 0, Niño3.4 = +4°C;
- 209 - RP+80%: peak in year 0, Niño3.4 = +4°C.

210 In this regard, even if there are substantial differences in the mechanisms involved, EN events are seen to be
211 independent from the timing of a sudden subsurface heat content reinforcement, given that the larger
212 warming rate in the RP+80% experiment quickly transforms the subsurface heat content into surface
213 temperature anomalies. This result provides support to the hypothesis that the transition from the tilting mode
214 to the recharge phase is a necessary step for the onset of EN events (Meinen and McPhaden 2000), and that it
215 cannot be fastened or bypassed by suddenly increasing the heat content in the western Pacific or in the whole
216 basin. In contrast, the timing and magnitude of EN episodes are substantially affected by the phase at which
217 a large decrease in heat content is prescribed, given that the restoring process reinforcing the heat content and
218 delaying the event by one year only takes place when heat is largely removed during the tilting mode:

- 219 - TM-80%: peak in year 1, Niño3.4 = +2°C;
- 220 - RP-80%: peak in year 0, Niño3.4 = +1.15°C.

221 No such behavior is instead seen if the decrease occurs later during the recharge phase.

222 The asymmetry in the response to the increased and decreased heat content scenarios is explained by
223 the direct relationship between the wind power (i.e. zonal wind stress acting on the kinetic energy of surface
224 currents) and the buoyancy power (i.e. anomalous tilt of the equatorial thermocline sustained by the kinetic
225 energy of the ocean currents, Brown et al. 2011). In the initially-increased experiments, the additional heat is
226 rapidly released regardless of the phase of the oscillation in which it is prescribed, because the unmodified
227 trade winds cannot sustain the anomalous slope of the thermocline resulting from the superimposed heat
228 content. Instead, in the initially-decreased experiments, the unmodified winds can sustain and eventually
229 reinforce the imposed more stable flatter slope of the thermocline. In this case, the response of the coupled
230 ocean-atmosphere system indeed depends on the stage of the oscillation (i.e. state of the thermocline) in which
231 the anomalous heat content is decreased.

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Figure 1. Longitude-time Hovmöller diagram of equatorial temperature (shading, in $^{\circ}\text{C}$) and zonal current (contour, in m/s) anomalies at the level of the thermocline.

Panels correspond to the observation composite of the December 1972, 1982 and 1997 El Niño events (a), the reference simulation (b), and a 80% reduction (d) or amplification (f) of the subsurface warming during the recharge phase. The other panels show the differences between the reference simulation and the observations (c) and between the recharge phase and tilting mode experiments (e,g). The minimum contour is $\pm 0.1 \text{ m/s}$ and the contour interval is 0.2 m/s , with grey solid (black dashed) lines depicting positive (negative) anomalies. The solid (dashed) green lines indicate the peak of El Niño (the recharge phase) in the reference simulation.

Figure 2. Longitude-time Hovmöller diagram of sea surface temperature (shading, in °C) and surface zonal wind (contour, in m/s) anomalies.

Panels correspond to the observation composite of the December 1972, 1982 and 1997 El Niño events (a), the reference simulation (b), and a 80% reduction (d) or amplification (f) of the subsurface warming during the recharge phase. The other panels show the differences between the reference simulation and the observations (c) and between the recharge phase and tilting mode experiments (e,g). The minimum contour is ± 0.5 m/s and the contour interval is 1 m/s, with grey solid (black dashed) lines depicting positive (negative) anomalies. The solid (dashed) green lines indicate the peak of El Niño (the recharge phase) in the reference simulation.

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SSH and Surface Zonal Currents

Figure 3. Longitude-time Hovmöller diagram of sea surface height (shading, in cm) and surface zonal current (contour, in m/s) anomalies.

Panels correspond to the observation composite of the December 1972, 1982 and 1997 El Niño events (a), the reference simulation (b), and a 80% reduction (d) or amplification (f) of the subsurface warming during the recharge phase. The other panels show the differences between the reference simulation and the observations (c) and between the recharge phase and tilting mode experiments (e,g). The minimum contour is ± 0.1 m/s and the contour interval is 0.2 m/s, with grey solid (black dashed) lines depicting positive (negative) anomalies. The solid (dashed) green lines indicate the peak of El Niño (the recharge phase) in the reference simulation.

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Figure 4. Longitude-time Hovmöller diagram of anomalies in equatorial temperature tendency at the level of the thermocline (shading, in °C/year) and the interhemispheric difference in wind stress curl between [0,20N] and [20S,0] (contour, in N/m³).

The panel corresponds to the observation composite of the December 1972, 1982 and 1997 El Niño events. The minimum contour is $\pm 0.5 \cdot 10^{-8}$ N/m³ and the contour interval is 10^{-8} N/m³, with grey solid (black dashed) lines depicting positive (negative) anomalies. The solid green line indicates the peak of El Niño.

Timing of subsurface heat magnitude for the growth of El Niño events

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Figure S1

Figure S1. Evolution of the Tropical Heat Content (10^{16} J) and the Niño3.4 Index ($^{\circ}$ C).

Lines correspond to the reference simulation (black), and a 80% reduction (cyan), a 40% reduction (magenta), a 40% amplification (red) and a 80% amplification (blue) of the subsurface warming during the recharge phase. The solid green lines indicate the peak of El Niño in the reference simulation. The Tropical Heat Content was computed as the temperature average within 120E-80W, 5S-5N and the upper 300m.

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